

ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF MODERN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND TRAINING

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CONTENTS

Section 1. MODERN PROBLEMS OF TOURISM AND ECONOMICS.....	4
BEKIMBETOVA GULNORA MARATOVNA /// EXPERTISE OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS IN THE CONDITIONS OF INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTERPRISES.....	4
Section 2. MODERN PROBLEMS OF PEDAGOGY AND PSYCHOLOGY.....	11
GOFUROVA SOJIDA SAYFULLAEVNA /// ADVANTAGES OF USING 3D TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING SPECIALIZED SUBJECTS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS.....	11
ELBOYEVA MADINA BOTIROVNA /// USING GESTURES TO IMPROVE LANGUAGE TEACHING.....	17
JUMABAYEVA MAHLIYO KHUDAIBERGAN DAUGHTER /// DIAGNOSIS OF PROFESSIONAL STRESS IN TEACHERS.....	22
Section 3. MODERN PROBLEMS OF PHILOLOGY AND LINGUISTICS.....	28
AQMANOVA SHAHNOZA ALIMBOYEVNA /// RELATION OF BIBLIONYM AND THE TEXT.....	28
DURNAZAROVA MAHLIYO, AKHMEDOVA MEHRINIGOR BAHODIROVNA /// ANALYSIS OF THE SHORT STORY “SHORT TERM HAPPINESS OF FRANCIS MACKOMBER”.....	34
RAKHMATOVA PARIZODA /// THE USE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ORAL AND WRITTEN LANGUAGES (ON THE BASE OF MATERIALS OF THE ART WORKS).....	38
Section 4. MODERN PROBLEMS OF TECHNICAL SCIENCES.....	43
KAZAKOVA DILAFRUZ ERKINOVNA, BARATOVA KUMISH MASHRAB QIZI, MUTALOVA YULDUZ ABDURAXMON QIZI /// ANALYSIS OF THE QUALITATIVE INDICATORS OF SPINNING YARNS FROM DIFFERENT GRADES OF COTTON.....	43
KHUDOYKULOV ZARIF RAHMATULLAEV ILHOM RAXMATULLAEVICH /// DEVELOPMENT OF A SOFTWARE STREAM ENCRYPTION ALGORITHM.....	51
MIRSANOV URALBOY MUHAMMADIEVICH, ISROILOV NURSHOKHRUKH SUNNAT UGLI /// A METHOD OF ORGANIZING PRACTICAL TRAINING IN SUBJECTS RELATED TO PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES.....	57
MADATOV KHABIBULLA AKHMEDOVICH, SATTAROVA SAPURA BEKNAZAROVNA /// METHODS OF CHECKING THE GIVEN LITERATURE ON THE INTELLECTUAL POTENTIAL OF SCHOOLCHILDREN.....	63

MATCHONOVA NARGIZ NORTOEVNA, ABBAZOV ILKHOM ZAPIROVICH /// CREATION OF FABRICS AND PRODUCTS OF FUNCTIONAL PURPOSE FROM LOCAL BASALT FIBER.....72

Section 5. ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF HISTORY, PHILOSOPHY AND SOCIOLOGY.....78

ARZIMATOVA INOYATXON MADIMAROVNA /// OFFICIAL ETIQUETTE AND SPEECH CULTURE DEVELOPMENT TASKS OF LEADERS.....78

BIYIMBETOV JAKSILIK KILISHBAYEVICH /// INFORMATION SECURITY OF SOCIETY AS A CURRENT PROBLEM (BASED ON EXPERIMENTAL TEST RESULTS).....83

ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF MATHEMATICS, PHYSICS AND MECHANICS

KARATAEVA SAODAT BOBIRXONOVNA, SARDORKHON AVAZKHONOVICH SAIDKHANOV, RANO BOBIRXONOVNA FOZILOVA /// IMPACT OF RADON ON THE HUMAN BODY AND HEALTH THREATS.....87

Section 7. ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF NATURAL SCIENCES.....95

AVEZOV SATTARBERGAN ATABAEVICH, GULIMMATOV IKROM BAKHTIYAROVICH, NORMETOV SUHROB MUHIDDIN OGLI /// UNIQUE TERRITORIAL FEATURES OF KHOREZM REGION'S URBANIZATION PROCESSES.....95

SHARIPOVA LOBAR AKRAMOVNA, KHUDOYBERGANOV OYBEK IKROMOVICH, IBRAGIMOVA MAVLUDA RUZMETOVNA, AZIZOV TOKHIR AZIZOVICH /// IR-SPECTROSCOPIC AND THERMAL ANALYSIS OF THE COORDINATION COMPOUNDS OF ZINC NITRATE WITH THIOUREA, BENZAMIDE AND BENZOIC ACID.....103

SHODIEV HAMZA RUZIKULOVICH /// THE METHOD OF ORGANIZING STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT LEARNING OF GEOGRAPHICAL SCIENCES.....109

TANIRBERGENOVA G., SEYTOVA N, DAULBAEVA K. /// ECOLOGICAL FEATURES NEAR-WATERS ROVE BEETLES (COLEOPTERA, STAPHYLINIDAE) SOUTHERN ARAL SEA.....115

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METHODS OF CHECKING THE GIVEN LITERATURE ON THE INTELLECTUAL POTENTIAL OF SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Annotatsiya: Ta'lim tizimida maktab o'quvchilarining yoshiga va ilmiy salohiyatiga mos bo'lgan darslik va boshqa manbalarni tanlash bugungi kundagi dolzarb muammolardan biridir. Ushbu maqolada "School corpus"dan foydalangan holda, boshlang'ich sinflar misolida matnlarning leksik o'xshashlik darajasidan foydalanib, maktab o'quvchilari uchun tavsiya etiladigan o'quv materiallarining o'quvchining intellektual salohiyatiga mosligini aniqlash masalasi xususida so'z boradi. Albatta, qo'yilgan masalani yechishning har xil yondashuvlari mavjud. Maqolada masalani yechishning TF-IDF ga asoslangan metodi qaraladi. Bunda matnlarning TF-IDFi aniqlanadi, ular vektorli ko'rinishga o'tkaziladi va matnlar o'xshashligining kosinus o'xshashlik algoritmi yordamida berilgan o'quv materiali "School corpus"ning tegishli sinfi bilan solishtiriladi. Hisoblash natijalariga ko'ra berilgan o'quv materiali o'quvchining ilmiy salohiyatiga mos yoki mos emasligi aniqlanadi. Maqolada qaralayotgan masala boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari misolida to'la hal qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ta'lim korpusi, darslik, leksik o'xshashlik, semantik o'xshashlik, kosinus o'xshashligi, atama chastotasi, teskari hujjat chastotasi

Аннотация: Выбор учебников и других ресурсов, соответствующих возрасту и научному потенциалу школьников в системе образования, является одной из самых актуальных проблем на сегодняшний день. В данной статье с помощью «Школьного корпуса», на уровне лексического сходства текстов на примере начальных классов, речь идет о проблеме определения совместимости рекомендуемых школьникам учебных материалов с интеллектуальным потенциалом учащегося. Конечно, есть разные подходы к решению проблемы. В статье рассматривается метод решения задачи на основе TF-IDF. При этом определяется TF-IDF текстов, они преобразуются в векторное представление и сравнивается соответствующий класс данного учебного материала «Школьный корпус» с использованием алгоритма косинусного сходства текстов. По результатам расчета определяется, подходит или не подходит данный учебный материал для учебного потенциала студента. рассматриваемый в статье вопрос в полной мере решен на примере учащихся начальных классов.

Ключевые слова: учебный корпус, учебник, лексическое сходство, семантическое сходство, косинусное сходство, частота термина, частота обратного документа.

Annotation: The choice of textbooks and other resources that correspond to the age and scientific potential of schoolchildren in the education system is one of the urgent issues today. In this article, with the help of the "School corpus", at the level of lexical similarity of texts on the example of primary school, we are talking about the problem of determining the compatibility of educational materials recommended for schoolchildren with the intellectual potential of the student. Of course, there are different approaches to solving the problem. The article highlights a method for solving the problem based on TF-IDF. Firstly, TF-IDF of texts is identified, then, they are converted into a vector representation, and the corresponding class of the given educational material "School corpus" is compared using the cosine text similarity algorithm. Based on the results of the calculation, it is determined whether the given educational material is suitable or not for the student's educational potential. The issue considered in the article is fully resolved on the example of primary school students.

Key words: educational corpus, textbook, lexical similarity, semantic similarity, cosine similarity, term frequency, inverse document frequency.

Introduction: Text similarity is one of the most advanced methods of text analysis in the field of NLP. Based on the sources studied so far, it is worth noting that the similarity of texts is used in a number of fields, such as information retrieval, text categorization, machine translation, and automatic essay evaluation. However, this article touches on about a new approach - providing schoolchildren with appropriate educational resources using the similarity of texts. The educational materials recommended for the use of students during the course of the lesson or outside of the lesson - their compatibility with their intellectual potential is one of the main criteria for the quality education of schoolchildren. This method, recommended by the author to improve the quality of education, is based on the "School corpus", which consists of a corpus of words that every student should know. This is the cosine of the similarity of the texts, which is suitable or not suitable for the student to master the stories, poems or other types of educational materials written by local or foreign writers, which are recommended to be employed in the educational process with the help of "School corpus". the issue of identification based on the similarity method is considered. Textbooks largely determine not only what topics and ideas are taught in the classroom but also the way they are presented to students (Stern and Roseman 2004, p. 539). Thus textbooks affect learning and teaching in many different ways. [1]. The textbook is just one of the tools that help teachers attain their educational goals. Teachers use teaching aids autonomously and plan individually when and how they will use them. In addition, teachers no longer have to follow the guidelines of one textbook, as several different textbooks are available for individual subjects. Teachers can choose the one that best suits both their teaching style and the specific characteristics of their students (Justin et al., 2003). Since the textbook is an important element of the teaching-learning process, the textbook politics must become part of the educational politics and receive more professional attention as well as a greater deal of systematic discussion (Turk Škraba, 2006). Learning from a textbook can only be efficient if it is adapted for students and vice versa, as this is the only way students are able to learn how to use effective learning strategies. Authors can adapt textbooks [2] to match the students' needs if they consider both the students' developmental stage as well as the level of

comprehension.

Similarity between words, sentences, paragraphs and documents is an important component in various tasks such as information retrieval, document clustering, word-sense disambiguation, automatic essay scoring, short answer grading, machine translation and text summarization. Text similarity means user's query text is matched with the document text and on the basis on this matching user retrieves the most relevant documents. Text similarity also plays an important role in the categorization of text as well as document. We can measure the similarity between sentences, words, paragraphs and documents to classify them in an efficient way. [3]

In Lexical similarity [4] provides the similarity on the basis of character and statement matching. Lexical similarity is a measure of the degree to which word set of two given string are similar. A Lexical similarity of 1 (means 100%) would mean a total overlap between words, Whereas Lexical similarity of 0 means there are no common word in given string.

Cosine similarity [5] measures the similarity between two vectors of an inner product space. It is measured by the cosine of the angle between two vectors and determines whether two vectors are pointing in roughly the same direction. It is often used to measure document similarity in text analysis. A document [6] can be represented by thousands of attributes, each recording the frequency of a particular word (such as a keyword) or phrase in the document. Thus, each document is an object represented by what is called *a* term-frequency vector.

Literature review: Uzbek researchers are conducting a number of scientific researches on text processing in the field of NLP. Because the creation of modern applications related to natural language processing, conducting scientific research will undoubtedly be an important factor in the development of any low-resource language. In today's era of rapid development of computer technologies and the Internet, any user is faced with relevant text processes such as searching for textual information, categorizing them, comparing and processing texts. One of the biggest challenges, especially when working with a large number of documents, is finding information that matches your interest. This problem can be easily solved by methods of determining the similarity of texts. Until now, many approaches have been developed by researchers to determine the similarity of words and texts.

The authors of the article [5] developed an algorithm for determining the similarity of cosines based on TF-IDF for texts in the Uzbek language. Removing stop words during text analysis reduces the size of the text and makes it easier to process the text [7] - the source lists stop words in the Uzbek language, [8] the article covers the issue of automatic detection of stop words in Uzbek texts. The article [9] presents a method for evaluating the quality of the list of stop words automatically determined from Uzbek texts. Also, in [10] stop words were identified using unigram, bigram and combination methods of "School Corpus" corresponding to the type of languages being studied. Semantic relationships between words are one of the key concepts in assessing natural language processing. In this paper [11], the authors present the SimRelUz-set dataset for evaluating the semantic model of the Uzbek language. One of the most common methods of processing textual data is TF-IDF. Google's search engine has been using the TF-IDF method to rank content relevant to user queries for many years.

This article [12] examines the process of sorting documents in the Uzbek language corpus in terms of using the TF-IDF method. Paper [13] defines different types of similarity like lexical similarity, semantic similarity. The article also effectively classifies the measurement of text similarity between sentences, words, paragraphs, and documents. Based on this classification, we can obtain the best relevant document that matches the user's request. Paper [14] presents a text semantic similarity measurement method, a corpus-based measure of word semantic similarity, and a normalized and modified version of the longest common subsequence (LCS) string matching algorithm. Existing methods for computing text similarity mainly focus on large documents or individual words. In this paper [15], research has been carried out on methods such as similarity calculation between Turkish text documents, plagiarism detection and author detection, text classification and clustering. In document analysis, an important task is to automatically find keywords which best describe the subject of the document. One of the most widely used techniques for keyword detection is a technique based on the term frequency-inverse document frequency (TF-IDF) heuristic. This techniques has some explanations, but these explanations are somewhat too complex to be fully convincing. In this paper [16], authors provide a simple probabilistic explanation for the TF-IDF heuristic. In [17], the authors defined a novel method for the vector representations of short texts. The method uses word embeddings and learns how to weigh each embedding based on its IDF value. The proposed method works with texts of a predefined length but can be extended to any length. The authors demonstrated showed that their method outperforms other baseline methods that aggregate word embeddings for modeling short texts.

In this article, using the "School Corpus", we provide information on the issue of determining the suitability of recommended educational materials for schoolchildren to the intellectual potential of students based on the lexical similarity of texts. The paper considers a problem solving method based on TF-IDF. The TF-IDFs of the texts are determined, they are converted into a vector, and the given educational material is compared with the corresponding class of the "School Corpus" using the cosine similarity algorithm of the text similarity. According to the calculation results, it is determined whether the given educational material corresponds to the student's scientific potential or not.

Research methodology: In this section, we describe the methodology adopted in the paper based on TF-IDF and cosine similarity of corpus-based texts.

Text Similarity: The main objective of text similarity is to analyze and measure how close two entities of text are to each other. These entities of text can be simple tokens or terms like words or whole documents, which may include sentences or paragraphs of text. There are various ways to analyze text similarity and we can classify the intent of text similarity broadly into the following two areas.

Lexical similarity: This involves observing the contents of the text documents with regards to its syntax, structure, and content and measuring their similarity based on these parameters.

Semantic similarity: This involves determining the semantics, meaning, and context of the documents and then determining how close they are to each other. Dependency grammars and entity recognition are handy tools that can help in this.

Term similarity: Similarity between individual tokens or words

Document similarity: Similarity between entire text documents [18]

Term Frequency – Inverse Document Frequency

Initially, we describe the concepts of TF and IDF [19]. Term Frequency - Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) is one of the statistical methods widely used in natural language processing and data mining. Within a document is a measure of how important a term is relative to the entire document. Words in a text document are converted to significant figures through a text vectorization process. Among the various text vectorization methods, TF-IDF is one of the most common.

Term Frequency: The TF of a term or word is a quantity that represents the number of occurrences of a term in a document relative to the total number of words in the document. [19]

$$TF = \frac{\text{number of times the term appears in the document}}{\text{total number of terms in the document}}$$

Inverse document frequency: A quantity that reflects the proportion of documents containing the term's term's IDF in the corpus. Words that are specific to a subset of documents will have a higher value than words that are common to all documents. [19]

$$IDF = \log\left(\frac{\text{number of the documents in the corpus}}{\text{number of documents in the corpus contain the term}}\right)$$

The TF-IDF of a term is calculated by multiplying TF and IDF scores.

$$TF-IDF = TF * IDF$$

There are different approaches to calculating the IDF score. The base 10 logarithms are often used in calculations. However, some libraries use the natural logarithm. It can also be added to the denominator to avoid division by zero [19]

$$IDF = \log\left(\frac{\text{number of the documents in the corpus}}{\text{number of documents in the corpus contain the term} + 1}\right)$$

Cosine Similarity – is a metric used to measure the similarity of two vectors. Specifically, it measures the similarity in the direction or orientation of the vectors ignoring differences in their magnitude or scale. Both vectors need to be part of the same inner product space, meaning they must produce a scalar through inner product multiplication. The similarity of two vectors is measured by the cosine of the angle between them.

How to calculate Cosine Similarity: We define cosine similarity mathematically [19] as the dot product of the vectors divided by their magnitude. For example, if we have two vectors, A and B, the similarity between them is calculated as:

Where

• θ is the angle between the vectors,

• $A \cdot B$ is the dot product between A and B

$$\text{similarity}(A, B) = \cos(\theta) = \frac{A \cdot B}{\|A\| \|B\|}$$

angle between

dot product

between A and B calculated as:

Figure 1: A detection algorithm using cosine similarity to determine the suitability of recommended educational materials for the schoolchildren to the intellectual potential of students using the "School Corpus".

- $A \cdot B = A^T B = \sum_{i=1}^n A_i B_i = A_1 B_1 + A_2 B_2 + \dots + A_n B_n$
- $\|A\|$ represents the L2 norm or magnitude of the vector which is calculated as $\|A\| = \sqrt{A_1^2 + A_2^2 + \dots + A_n^2}$
- The similarity can take values between 0 and +1. Smaller angles between vectors produce larger cosine values, indicating greater cosine similarity. For example:
 - When two vectors have the same orientation, the angle between them is 0, and the cosine similarity is 1.
 - Perpendicular vectors have a 90-degree angle between them and a cosine similarity of 0.

Analysis and results: Initially, 9 textbooks of the 1st, 2nd and 3rd grades, as well as 8 of the 4th, were downloaded from <https://kitob.uz/>. These books were then converted from pdf to txt format and tokenized. As a result, the School Corpus was created as part of the following numbers. Class 1 corpus has 24107 tokens, 7978 unique words, class 2 has 56650 tokens, 14858 unique words, class 3 has 90255 tokens, 21124 unique words, and class 4 corpus has 109024 tokens and 24736 unique words. The total number of unique primary school words was 42797.

Table 1: List of sources that we investigated in this article

(This table lists the elementary school bases as well as one text from each one, and children’s literature texts from the Internet)

№	FILE NAME	SOURCE NAME
1	corpus_1.txt	Total textbooks for 1st grade
2	corpus_2.txt	Total textbooks for 2nd grade
3	corpus_3.txt	Total textbooks for 3rd grade
4	corpus_4.txt	Total textbooks for 4th grade
5	1_qor.txt	1 st grade
6	Toshkent.txt	2 nd grade
7	hikoya.txt	3 rd grade
8	kichik_vatan	4 th grade text
9	ayiq.txt	https://gulxan.uz/ertaklar/ayiqpolvonning-xatosi
10	gulxan.txt	https://gulxan.uz/hikoyalar/aybsiz-aybdor
11	vatan.txt	https://hozir.org/ozbekiston-vatanim-mening.html
12	sariq_dev.txt	X.To’xtaboyev:” Sariq devni minib” asari

Table 2: File comparison: (In the process of defining file similarities, after comparing the text from the corresponding stage of the school bases with it, their cosine similarity was equal to 1, and in the other cases, the result was $0 < \cos A < 1$)

Results of applying cosine similarity to Uzbek texts

No	Files	corpus_1.txt	corpus_2.txt	corpus_3.txt	corpus_4.txt
	corpus_1.txt	1	0.866	0.864	0.851
	corpus_2.txt	0.866	1	0.953	0.928
	corpus_3.txt	0.864	0.953	1	0.967
	corpus_4.txt	0.851	0.928	0.967	1
	1_qor.txt	1	0.187	0.183	0.189
	Toshkent.txt	0.387	1	0.414	0.443
	hikoya.txt	0.266	0.236	1	0.244
	kichik_vatan.txt	0.408	0.412	0.428	1
	ayiq.txt	0.245	0.295	0.288	0.296
0	gulxan.txt	0.304	0.285	0.289	0.293
1	vatan.txt	0.625	0.617	0.673	0.712
2	sariq_dev.txt	0.35	0.335	0.322	0.329

According to the final results, the cosine similarity algorithm of the Uzbek language texts in accordance with the sources listed in Table1 was achieved using the Python programming language, and the results listed in Table2 were obtained. We can witness that the cosine similarity between the base and its derived text is 1, otherwise cosine similarity results $0 < \cos A < 1$. The essence of our article is that we have determined the cosine similarity of the educational material that is recommended to the schoolchildren using the algorithm shown in Figure1. Based on the result of the maximum cosine similarity, we can conclude which class the given educational material corresponds to.

Conclusion. As we all know, the 2023 was named "The year of human care and quality education". Providing educational materials suitable for the intellectual potential of primary school students is an important factor in improving the quality of education. In this regard, the creation of similarity algorithms of texts and textbooks in the Uzbek language is an important process. Because of this article we have achieved this attainments:

1. We presented the first "School Corpus" dataset with more than 109 024 tokens based on elementary school textbooks.
2. In addition, a TF-IDF-based cosine similarity algorithm was developed for Uzbek language texts, and it was tested based on the elementary school corpus, and the final

results were obtained based on the Python programming language.

3. Using the cosine similarity algorithm for determining the similarity of texts presented in the article, it is recommended to determine the similarity of not only school educational materials, but also literary genres of any kind.

In the future, researchers plan to apply other similarity algorithms, including neural network methods, to texts in the Uzbek language. Moreover, the researchers aim to expand additional datasets from different fields. Besides that, researchers will develop more sophisticated NLP similarity algorithms and tools for the Uzbek language.

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CREATION OF FABRICS AND PRODUCTS OF FUNCTIONAL PURPOSE FROM LOCAL BASALT FIBER

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada qo'shimcha qiymat yaratishga yo'nalgan noan'anaviy materiallar, funksional maqsadli mato va ularni yaralashlari bazalt xom ashyosi bilan bog'liq holda to'qilgan.

Bazalt mato va erkinlar yukori mustahkamlikka yonmaydi, olovbardosh, +980 0S gacha o'zlitligini saqlaydigan, elektromagnit nurlanishga, namlikka, tuzatishga chidamli, kimyoviy ishga hamda elektroizolyasion to'g'ri keladi. Yuqorida keltiriladigan narsalarga bazaltdan foydalanishga oid amaliy materiallarga, yordamga va qo'shishga qiymat yaratishga yo'naltirilgan innovatsion kompozitsion materiallar, funktsiyaga mos keladigan vaziyatlarni ishga tushirishga bag'ishlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: bazalt, bazalt tolasi, roving, shnur, o'rganilgan armaturali roving, trikotaj, eng, kompozit.

Аннотация. В данной статье интерпретируются возможности создания нетрадиционных материалов, тканей функционального назначения и изделий, направленных на создание добавленной стоимости, применительно к базальтовому сырью.

Базальтовые ткани и изделия отличаются высокой прочностью, негорючесть и огнестойки, сохраняют целостность до +980 °С, устойчивы к электромагнитному излучению, влаге, коррозии, устойчивы к химическому